

Formulation and Evaluation of Cefixime Loaded Grafted Gellan Gum Tablet

Tejaram*¹, Rajesh Sharma², Prashant Purohit³, Sanju⁴ and Kashi Ram⁵

¹Research Scholar, ²Professor, Alwar Pharmacy College, Alwar, Rajasthan 301001.

^{3, 4&5} Assistant Professor, Swami Keshvanand Institute of Pharmacy, Rajasthan 334001.

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*Corresponding Author Email: tejalpanwar804@gmail.com

Abstract

The objective of the present work is to design sustained release tablets of cefixime by incorporating drug with polymer using microwave assisted graft co-polymerization method. In the present study, Gellan gum was used as a polysaccharide and grafted with acrylamide to make a sustained release formulation of cefixime which can solve mainly problem associated with multiple dose frequency and it can also increase patient compliance. The effect of combination of polymers on parameters like release pattern, release mechanism of the drug were studied. Preparation of total Seven formulation A1, A2, A3, A4, A5, A6 and A7 each containing gellan gum and acrylamide. The characterization of optimized formulation A6 was evaluated for Average time (75 sec), weight of grafted gum (3.029 gm), % yield (84.138%), % Grafting (202.9%) and % Grafting Efficiency (57.971%). Cefixime matrix tablets were formulated successfully by changing the excipient amount in four batches A6a, A6b, A6c, A6d and evaluated for the various parameters as per Indian Pharmacopoeia like Thickness (3.37 ± 0.588 mm), Weight Variation (405 ± 2.36 mg), Hardness (6.3 Kg/cm^2), Friability (0.44% weight loss), Disintegration Time (4.25 ± 0.110 min), and Uniformity of content (96.022 ± 0.113 %). In vitro release profiles of all batches were carried out in simulated gastric fluid pH 1.2 and simulated intestinal fluid pH 7.2 for upto 10 hr. From in vitro release studies, it was found that 81% drug was released in A6c in 10 h. From the result it was confirmed that grafting formed gives sustain drug delivery system.

Keywords

cefixime, sustained release, polymer, acrylamide

INTRODUCTION:

Infectious diseases are most common in developing countries. The infectious bacterial classes are both Gram positive and Gram negative hence, the treatment is necessary with an agent, which have

broad spectrum of activity. Cephalosporins possess a wide range of activity against Gram positive and Gram negative bacteria; these are act by inhibiting bacterial cell wall synthesis. Cefixime is an orally active third generation cephalosporins

Figure 1: Cefixime

The objectives of the present work are to design, formulate and evaluate matrix tablets of cefixime for sustained release dosage form. As the effect of sustained release dosage form is relatively more, incorporating the drug in the matrix tablet will prolong the drug release. These are prepared by direct compression method.

A polymer is a macromolecule which is poised of repeating structural units i.e. monomer and this structural unit are connected to each other via covalent bonds. Polysaccharides are the polymers comprising of monosaccharides connected to each other via glycoside linkage.

Grafted co-polymer includes a previously formed polymer backbone onto which the other species of polymer chains, which are of varying chemical natures, are attached at different sites of the polymeric backbone. The connected side chains may be comprises of a monomeric unit or of a binate mix. The one which is having one monomer only is easier to synthesize and generally happens in a solitary

step, nevertheless grafting in the case of binate blend requires to be done in continuous and stepwise addition of the monomers.

The Gellan Gum is one of the anionic polysaccharides that have a linear structure composed of a tetrasaccharide-repeating sequence that comprises one α -L-rhamnose, one β -D-glucuronate and two residues of β -D-glucose. Gellan Gum naturally exists in acylated form, yet its deacylation can be formed by alkaline hydrolysis.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Chemical and Reagents

Cefixime was purchased from KAPL., Bengaluru, India, Acrylamide were purchased from Sisco research laboratories Pvt Ltd, Mumbai, India. Gellan Gum was purchased from Qualikem, Mumbai, India. HCl and methanol were purchased from SD Fine-chem. Ltd, Mumbai.

Identification of Pure Drug and Polymers

Figure 2: DSC of Cefixime

Figure 3: FTIR of Cefixime

Figure 4: FTIR of Acrylamide

Figure 5: FTIR of Gellan Gum

Preparation of Grafted gum

Gallen gum (2 g) was slowly dispersed in 100 ml water in a three-necked round bottom flask and allowed to hydrate for 4 h with continuous purging of a slow stream of nitrogen gas. Acrylamide (2-3 g) and potassium persulfate (0.05-0.150 gm) were added to solution and irradiated to microwaves at 440 W under different time (60-90seconds) to carry out the polymerization reaction. The resulting copolymer was allowed to cool to ambient temperature and then poured into 400 ml acetone. The product was filtered and washed with excess amount of aqueous methanol (30% v/v) to remove the homopolymer of Acrylamide. The co-polymer was then

dried overnight at 50°C to constant weight. Finally the product was stored in vacuum desiccators until use as given in Table 1. The percentages yield, grafting and grafting efficiency were calculated using the following formula:

$$\% \text{ Yield} = \frac{\text{Weight of Grafted Gum}}{\text{Theoretical weight}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

$$\% \text{ Grafting} = \frac{W_1 - W_0}{W_0} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

$$\% \text{ Grafting Efficiency} = \frac{W_1}{W_0 + W_1} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

Where W_0 , W_1 and W_2 denote the weights of gellan, graft co-polymer and Aam, respectively

Table 1: Grafting parameters from various batches of microwave-assisted grafting.

S.No	Formulation code	Gum weight (gm)	Acrylamide weight (gm)	Amount of initiator (gm)	Power (Watt)	Time (sec)
1	A1	1	2.5	0.05	440	60
2	A2	1	2.5	0.1	440	60
3	A3	1	2.5	0.15	440	60
4	A4	1	2	0.1	440	60
5	A5	1	3	0.1	440	60
6	A6	1	2.5	0.1	440	75

Figure 6: FTIR interpretation data of A6 gellan-gum and Acrylamide

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

Preparation Gellan Gum Acrylamide matrix tablets of Cefixime

Matrix tablets of cefixime were prepared employing graft copolymer as the matrix. The required quantity of cefixime was blended with grafted gellan gum and acrylamide in different proportions along with

magnesium stearate as lubricant, Talc and Microcrystalline cellulose. The dry blend so obtained was directly compressed using 8 mm biconvex punches and dies in a single station hand-operated, tablet punching machine (R&D model, Konark Instruments, Ambala, India).

Table2: Composition of grafted tablets of Cefixime

S.No	Formulation code	Drug (mg)	Grafted Gum (mg)	Microcrystalline cellulose (mg)	Talc (mg)	Magnesium stearate (mg)	Total weight (mg)
1	A6a	200	100	60	20	20	400
2	A6b	200	125	35	20	20	400
3	A6c	200	150	10	20	20	400
4	A6d	200	175	5	10	10	400

Evaluation of tablets

The matrix tablets of cefixime were evaluated for thickness, weight variation, hardness, friability,

content uniformity and in vitro release as per Indian Pharmacopoeia 2010.

Table 3: Values of physical parameters of Cefixime tablets containing gellan gum Acrylamide

S.No	Batch code	Thickness (mm)	Weight Variation (mg)	Hardness (Kg/cm ²)	Friability (% weight loss)	Disintegration Time (minutes)	Uniformity of content (%)
1	A6a	3.26±0.872	401±1.61	5.6	0.48%	3.30±0.102	90.416±0.065
2	A6b	3.35±0.567	404±2.03	6.6	0.39%	5.42±0.007	92.159±0.113
3	A6c	3.37±0.588	405±2.36	6.3	0.44%	4.25±0.110	96.022±0.113
4	A6d	3.40±0.921	405±2.44	6.8	0.36%	5.50±0.101	93.712±0.065

In-Vitro Drug Release Studies

The optimized batch of grafted gellan-g-Aam was carried for in vitro drug release studies. The in vitro drug release study of A6c matrix tablet and UN-SA matrix tablet was carried out for 10 hours in simulated gastric fluid (SGF) pH 1.2 for the 2 h, followed by simulated intestinal fluid (SIF) pH 7.2. A6c matrix tablet has provided sustained release of the drug from tablet as compared to the tablet

prepared from ungrafted gum. Drug released from the A6c tablet was in controlled manner as compared to the ungraftedUN-gallen tablet. The drug content in each sample was analyzed by UV-VIS spectrophotometer at 288 nm. It was observed from the results that the matrix tablet of A6c released the maximum drug within 8 hours as compared to UN-gallen. A6c compressed tablets was able to sustain

the drug release up to 10 hours so this may be the suitable polymer for sustain drug delivery.

Figure 7: In vitro cumulative % release of drug between A6c

Table 4: In vitro cumulative % drug release of A6c

S.No	Time (hour)	Cumulative % Release of A6c formulation (Mean±S.D) n=3
1	0.25	7.158±0.090
2	0.5	14.676±0.285
3	1	17.470±0.636
4	2	37.705±0.734
5	3	38.411±0.713
6	4	47.764±0.269
7	5	56±0.619
8	6	65.294±0.176
9	7	73±0.269
10	8	78±0.305
11	9	79.941±0.176
12	10	81.176±0.529

Drug release kinetics

To explore and explain the mechanism of drug released from the matrix tablets, formulations were subjected to the modelling and release kinetic

studies such as zero order, first order, Higuchi model and Korsmeyer–Peppas model.

Figure 8: Zero order release kinetics of A6c

Figure 9: First order release kinetics of A6c

Figure 10: Higuchi model release kinetics of A6c

Figure 11: Korsmeyer-Peppas model release kinetics of A6c

Table 5: Kinetic equation parameter of A6c formulation

Formulation Name	Zero order		First order		Higuchi		Korsmeyer-peppas	
	R ²	K ₀	R ²	K ₀	R ²	K ₀	R ²	K ₀
A6c	0.949	8.122	0.982	-0.170	0.985	28.16	0.984	1.496

The values of regression coefficient (R^2) from the different drug release kinetic models are tabulated in **table**. The results of the modelling study revealed that release of drug from the matrix tablets of A6c tablet of cefixime fitted best into Higuchi model with the maximum values of R^2 while the value of n characterizes the release mechanism of drug. For the case of matrix tablets, $0.45 \leq n$ corresponds to fickian diffusion mechanism, $0.45 < n < 0.89$ to non-fickian transport, $n = 0.89$ to case II (relaxational) transport, and $n > 0.89$ to super case II transport [102]. The n values for the tablet A6c is more than 1, it revealed that the mechanism of drug release was a super case-II transport indicating the drug release rate does not change over time and the release is characterized by zero order.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

A graft co-polymer is a macromolecular chain with one or more polymer attached to the main chain. Therefore, it may be described as, having the general structure, where the main polymer backbone, commonly referred to as the trunk polymer, having branches of another polymeric chain. Graft copolymerization of natural polysaccharide backbone is one of the best ways to use polysaccharide for controlled drug delivery. Microwave assisted graft copolymerization is an efficient method.

Cefixime was selected as the drug candidate for the present study for its immense potential as an antibiotic. Further, its short half-life (3-4 hr) of administration, feasible analytical methodology for

its in vitro studies and high physicochemical stability makes it an ideal drug for oral sustain release dosage form. FT-IR spectrum, UV-VIS spectrum and melting point studies confirmed the identity and purity of obtained sample of Cefixime. Solubility profile was analyzed and log P confirmed its hydrophilic nature. Gellan gum was selected as a natural polymer for grafting with acrylamide which is a natural polymer and gellan gum Acrylamide was prepared by Microwave assisted method. Different formulations were prepared using the various amount of acrylamide and microwave time of exposure formulation with highest percentage grafting efficiency was considered as optimized formulation. The matrix tablets of Cefixime were prepared by using drug, polymer, diluents and lubricant blended in pestle mortar followed by direct compression in a single punching machine.

The matrix tablets of to check for weight variation, hardness, friability, disintegration time and drug content as per I.P. and were found to be within the specified limits.

In vitro release profiles of all batches and marketed formulation were carried out in simulated gastric fluid pH 1.2 and simulated intestinal fluid pH 7.2 for upto 10 hr. From in vitro release studies, it was found that 81% drug was released in A6c in 10 h. From the result it was confirmed that grafting formed gives sustained drug delivery system.

REFERENCE:

1. Sabyasachi M. Polysaccharide-Based Graft Copolymers in Controlled Drug Delivery. *Pharm Tech.* 2010; 2:1350-8.
2. Sartaz Ali NP. Extraction and evaluation of *Lallemantia royleana* seed mucilage. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences.* 2016;5(6):1056-66.
3. Atabaki R, Hassanpour-Ezatti M. Improvement of Lidocaine Local Anesthetic Action Using *Lallemantia royleana* Seed Mucilage as an Excipient. *Iran J Pharm Res.* 2014;13(4):1431-6.
4. Bharat W, Tekade YAC. Gums and Mucilages: Excipients for modified Drug Delivery System. *Journal of Advanced Pharmacy Education & Research.* 2013;3(4):350-67.
5. Jani GK, Shah, DP, Prajapati, VD, Jain V. C. Gums and mucilages: versatile excipients for pharmaceutical formulations. *Asian J Pharm Sci.* 2009;4(5):309-23.
6. Brostow W, HEHL, SP, Singh RP. Polymeric flocculants for wastewater and industrial effluent treatment. *Journal of Materials Education.* 2009; 31:157-66.
7. Beneke CE, Viljoen, AM, Hamman JH. Polymeric Plant-derived Excipients. *Drug Delivery.* 2009; 14:2602-20.
8. Setia A, Kumar R. Microwave assisted synthesis and optimization of *Aegle marmelos*-g-poly(acrylamide): release kinetics studies. *Int J Biol Macromol.* 2014; 65: 462-70.
9. Malviya R, Sharma PK, Dubey SK. Modification of Polysaccharides: Pharmaceutical and Tissue Engineering Applications with Commercial Utility (Patents). *Mater Sci Eng C Mater Biol Appl.* 2016 Nov 1; 68:929-938.
10. Thakur VK, Thakur MK. Recent Advances in Graft Copolymerization and Applications of Chitosan: A Review. *ACS Sustainable Chemistry & Engineering.* 2014; 2(12): 2637-2652.
11. Moghimipour E, Aghel N, Adelpour A. Formulation and Characterization of Oral Mucoadhesive Chlorhexidine Tablets Using *Cordia myxa* Mucilage. *Jundishapur J Nat Pharm Prod.* 2012; 7(4):129-33.
12. Duan W, Chen C, Jiang L, Li GH. Preparation and characterization of the graft copolymer of chitosan with poly[rosin-(2-acryloyloxy) ethyl ester]. *Carbohydrate Polymers.* 2008;73(4):582-6.
13. Rani P, Sen G, Mishra S, Jha U. Microwave assisted synthesis of polyacrylamide grafted gum ghatti and its application as flocculant. *Carbohydrate Polymers.* 2012; 89(1):275-81.
14. Pal S, Nasim T, Patra A, Ghosh S, Panda AB. Microwave assisted synthesis of polyacrylamide grafted dextrin (Dxt-g-PAM): Development and application of a novel polymeric flocculant. *Int J Biol Macromol.* 2010; 47(5):623-31.
15. Meenkashi, Ahuja M, Verma P. MW-assisted synthesis of carboxymethyl tamarind kernel polysaccharide-g-polyacrylonitrile: optimization and characterization. *Carbohydr Polym.* 2014; 26 (113) :532-8.
16. Kumar A, Singh K, Ahuja M. Xanthan-g-poly(acrylamide): Microwave-assisted synthesis, characterization and in vitro release behavior. *Carbohydrate Polymers.* 2009;76(2):261-7.
17. Vijan V, Kaity S, Biswas S, Isaac J, Ghosh A. Microwave assisted synthesis and characterization of acrylamide grafted gellan, application in drug delivery. *Carbohydrate Polymers.* 2012;90(1):496-506.
18. Malik S, Ahuja M. Gum kondagogu-g-poly (acrylamide): Microwave-assisted synthesis, characterisation and release behaviour. *Carbohydrate Polymers.* 2011;86(1):177-84.
19. Singh AV, Nath LK, Guha M. Microwave assisted synthesis and characterization of *Phaseolus aconitifolius* starch-g-acrylamide. *Carbohydrate Polymers.* 2011;86(2):872-6.
20. Tiwari A, Singh V. Microwave-induced synthesis of electrical conducting gum acacia-graft-polyaniline. *Carbohydrate Polymers.* 2008;74(3):427-34.
21. Mishra S, Usha Rani G, Sen G. Microwave initiated synthesis and application of polyacrylic acid grafted carboxymethyl cellulose. *Carbohydrate Polymers.* 2012;87(3):2255-62.
22. Singh V, Tiwari A, Tripathi DN, Sanghi R. Microwave assisted synthesis of Guar-g-polyacrylamide. *Carbohydrate Polymers.* 2004;58(1):1-6.
23. Silva DA, de Paula RCM, Feitosa JPA. Graft copolymerisation of acrylamide onto cashew gum. *European Polymer Journal.* 2007;43(6):2620-2629.
24. Mishra A, Malhotra AV. Graft copolymers of xyloglucan and methyl methacrylate. *Carbohydrate Polymers.* 2012;87(3):1899-1904.
25. Sen G, Mishra S, Rani GU, Rani P, Prasad R. Microwave initiated synthesis of polyacrylamide grafted *Psyllium* and its application as a flocculant. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules.* 2012;50(2):369-375.
26. Rani P, Mishra S, Sen G. Microwave based synthesis of polymethyl methacrylate grafted sodium alginate: its application as flocculant. *Carbohydrate Polymers.* 2013;91(2):686-692.
27. Mishra A, Pal S. Polyacrylonitrile-grafted *Okra* mucilage: A renewable reservoir to polymeric materials. *Carbohydrate Polymers.* 2007;68(1):95-100.
28. Sosnik A, Gotelli G, Abraham GA. Microwave-assisted polymer synthesis (MAPS) as a tool in biomaterials science: How new and how powerful. *Progress in Polymer Science.* 2011;36(8):1050-1078.
29. Singh AV, Nath LK. Evaluation of acetylated moth bean starch as a carrier for controlled drug delivery. *Int J Biol Macromol.* 2012;50(2):362-8.
30. Bhosale RR, Gangadharappa H V, Moin A, Gowda D V, Osmani RAM. Grafting Technique with Special Emphasis on Natural Gums : Applications and Perspectives in Drug Delivery Grafting Technique with Special Emphasis on Natural Gums : Applications and Perspectives in Drug Delivery. 2015.
31. Khan F, Ahmad SR. Polysaccharides and their derivatives for versatile tissue engineering application. *Macromol Biosci.* 2013; 13(4):395-421
32. Patel D. Microwave assisted heating -an alternative to conventional heating in pharmaceutical research. *International Journal of Advances in Pharmaceutical Research.* 2011;2(3):87-95.

33. Himanshu K, Solanki VDP, Jani GK. Microwave Technology - A Potential Tool in Pharmaceutical Science. *Int. J PharmTech Res.* 2010; 2(3): 1754-1761.
34. Monika Gupta SPaRG. General Characteristics and Applications of Microwaves in Organic Synthesis. *Acta Chim Slov.* 2009; 56:749-764.
35. Kappe CO. Controlled Microwave Heating in Modern Organic Synthesis. *Angewandte Chemie International Edition.* 2004; 43 (46):6250-6284.
36. Lidstrom P, Tierney J, Wathey B, Westman J. Microwave assisted organic synthesis—a review. *Tetrahedron.* 2001; 57(45): 9225-9283.
37. Ahmed EM. Hydrogel: Preparation, characterization, and applications: A review. *J Adv Res.* 2015; 6(2):105-21.
38. Garnett SDJL. Radiation-induced reactions with cellulose. III. Kinetics of styrene copolymerization in methanol. *Applied Polymer.* 1967;11(6):859-70.
39. Alfaifi AYA, El-Newehy MH, Abdel HES, Al-Deyab SS. Microwave-assisted graft copolymerization of amino acid based monomers onto starch and their use as drug carriers. *Carbohydrate Polymers.* 2014;106:440-52.
40. Loo-Teck Ng, John LGarnett, Elvis Zilic, Duc Nguyen. Effect of monomer structure on radiation grafting of charge transfer complexes to synthetic and naturally occurring polymers. *Radiation Physics and Chemistry.* 2001;62(1):89-98.
41. Hongfei H, Wu L, Tai H, Zhang Z, Wei J, Wu J. Proceedings of the 29th International Meeting on Radiation Processing Study of radiation grafting of styrene on cotton cellulose. *Radiation Physics and Chemistry.* 1995; 1995/10/01;46(4):823-7.
42. Garnett JL, Jankiewicz SV, Sangster DF. Mechanistic aspects of the acid and salt effect in radiation grafting. *International Journal of Radiation Applications and Instrumentation Part C Radiation Physics and Chemistry.* 1990; 36 (4): 571-9.
43. Ulbricht M. Advanced functional polymer membranes. *Polymer.* 2006; 47(7): 2217-2262.
44. Joshi JM, Sinha VK. Synthesis and Characterization of Carboxymethyl Chitosan Grafted Methacrylic Acid Initiated by Ceric Ammonium Nitrate. *Journal of Polymer Research.* 2006;13(5):387-395.
45. Rana V, Rai P, Tiwary AK, Singh RS, Kennedy JF, Knill CJ. Modified gums: Approaches and applications in drug delivery. *Carbohydrate Polymers.* 2011;83(3):1031-1047.
46. Sathish Ummadi BS, N. G. Raghavendra Rao, M. Srikanth Reddy, B. Sanjeev Nayak. Overview on Controlled Release Dosage Form. *International Journal of Pharma Sciences.* 2013;3:258-269.
47. Mehrdad Mahkam Ap. Synthesis And Characterization Of Polymeric Nanocapsules As Colon-Specific Drug Delivery System. 2012; 4(4).
48. Mishra S, Sen G. Microwave initiated synthesis of polymethylmethacrylate grafted guar (GG-g-PMMA), characterizations and applications. *Int J Biol Macromol.* 2011; 48(4): 688-694.
49. Pal S, Ghorai S, Dash MK, Ghosh S, Udayabhanu G. Flocculation properties of polyacrylamide grafted carboxymethyl guar gum (CMG-g-PAM) synthesised by conventional and microwave assisted method. *Journal of Hazardous Materials.* 2011;192(3):1580-1588.
50. Wang B, Li J, Zhang J, Li H, Chen P, Gu Q, et al. Thermo-mechanical properties of the composite made of poly (3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate) and acetylated chitin nanocrystals. *Carbohydrate Polymers.* 2013;95(1):100-106.
51. Shailaja TLK, Sasibhushan P, Alkabab AM, Uhumwangho MU. A novel bioadhesive polymer: grafting of tamarind seed polysaccharide and evaluation of its use in buccal delivery of metoprolol succinate. *Scholar Research Library.* 2012;4(2):487-508.
52. Indian Pharmacopoeia 2010 Volume II. Published by Indian Pharmacopoeia Commission, Ghaziabad. 1012-1014.
53. Indian Pharmacopoeia 2010 Volume I. Published by Indian Pharmacopoeia Commission, Ghaziabad. 177.
54. <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/cefixime#section=Computed-Properties>
55. Md. Ahasan Ullah Nayon, Jeb-Un Nesa, Md. Nasir Uddin, Md. Shah Amran, Umme Bushra. Development and validation of UV Spectrometric Method for the Determination of Cefixime. *Asian Journal of Biomedical and Pharmaceutical Sciences;* 3(22) 2013, 1-5.
56. <https://www.drugbank.ca/drugs/DB00671>.
57. Leggett NJ, Caravaggio C, Rybak MJ. Cefixime. *DICP.* 1990; 24(5):489-95.
58. Cable CG. Sodium alginate; 2009. *Handbook of Pharmaceutical excipients*, 6th edition. Pharmaceutical Press, London, UK.
59. Vattem DA, Shetty K. Acrylamide in food: a model for mechanism of formation and its reduction. *Innovative Food Science & Emerging Technologies.* 2003;4(3):331-338.
60. Lande SS, Bosch SJ, Howard PH. Degradation and leaching of acrylamide in soil. *Journal of Environmental Quality.* 1979;8(1):133-137.
61. Spencer PS, Schaumburg HH. A review of acrylamide neurotoxicity Part I. Properties, uses and human exposure. *Canadian Journal of Neurological Sciences/Journal Canadien des Sciences Neurologiques.* 1974; 1(2):143-150.
62. Index TM. Published by Merck Research Laboratories Division Of Merck & Co., INC, Whitehouse station, Nj, USA, edition - 14. 2006:22.
63. Kaity S, Isaac J, Kumar PM, Bose A, Wong TW, Ghosh A. Microwave assisted synthesis of acrylamide grafted locust bean gum and its application in drug delivery. *Carbohydr Polym.* 2013;98(1):1083-1094
64. Dan S, Mandal P, Bose A, Pal TK. Microwave Assisted Acrylamide Grafting on a Natural Gum Cassia Tora: Characterization and Pharmacokinetic Evaluation of the Formulation Containing Metformin and Sitagliptin in Rats by LC-MS/MS. *TACL; 8 (5) 2018 pp 622 – 641.*
65. Soni SR, Kumari N, Bhunia BK, Sarkar B, Mandal BB, Ghosh A. In vitro and in vivo evaluation of pirfenidone loaded acrylamide grafted pullulanpoly (vinyl alcohol) interpenetrating polymer networks, *Carbohydrate Polymers,* 2018.

66. Badwaik HR, Sakure K, Nakhate KT, Kashayap P, Dhongade H, Alexander A, Ajazuddin, Tripathi DK. Effect of Ca²⁺ ion on the release of diltiazem hydrochloride from matrix tablets of carboxymethyl xanthan gum graft polyacrylamide. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*, 94 (2017) 691–697.
67. Kaity S, Ghosh A. Facile preparation of acrylamide grafted locust bean gum poly (vinyl alcohol) interpenetrating polymer network microspheres for controlled oral drug delivery, *Journal of Drug Delivery Science and Technology*. 2016.
68. Giri TK, Pure S, Tripathi DK. Synthesis of graft copolymers of acrylamide for locust bean gum using microwave energy: swelling behavior, flocculation characteristics and acute toxicity study. *Polimeros*. 2015; 25:168-74.
69. Mittal H, Maity A, Ray SS. Gum ghatti and poly(acrylamide-co-acrylic acid) based biodegradable hydrogel-evaluation of the flocculation and adsorption properties. *Polymer Degradation and Stability*. 2015; 120:42-52.
70. Tang XJ, Huang J, Xu L-Y, Li Y, Song J, Ma Y, et al. Microwave-assisted rapid synthesis, characterization and application of poly (d,l-lactide)-graft-pullulan. *Carbohydrate Polymers*. 2014; 107:7-15.
71. Pandey VS, Verma SK, Behari K. Graft [partially carboxymethylated guar gum-g-poly N-(hydroxymethyl) acrylamide] copolymer: From synthesis to applications. *Carbohydrate Polymers*. 2014; 110:285-91.
72. Bruno D, Mattos ALM, Pedro HG de C, Darci AG, Washington LEM. Wood-polymer composites prepared by in situ polymerization of methyl methacrylate using bi-functional additive. 2014; 25.
73. Setia A, Kumar R. Microwave assisted synthesis and optimization of Aegle marmelos-g-poly(acrylamide): release kinetics studies. *Int J Biol Macromol*. 2014; 65: 462-470.
74. Sorour M, El Sayed M, El Moneem NA, Talaat H, Shaalan H, El Marsafy S. Free radical grafting kinetics of acrylamide onto a blend of starch/chitosan/alginate. *Carbohydr Polym*. 2013; 98(1):460-464.
75. Vijan V, Kaity S, Biswas S, Isaac J, Ghosh A. Microwave assisted synthesis and characterization of acrylamide grafted gellan, application in drug delivery. *Carbohydrate Polymers*. 2012;90(1):496-506.
76. Rajendra A, Prashant P, Shivakumar S, Sridhar BK. Preparation and evaluation of extended release matrix tablets of diltiazem using blends of tamarind xyloglucan with gellan gum and sodium carboxymethyl cellulose. *Der Pharmacia Lettre*. 2011;3:380-392
77. Pareek A, Chandurkar N, Gupta A, Arunangshu M. Efficacy and safety of aceclofenac-CR and aceclofenac in the treatment of knee osteoarthritis: a 6-week, comparative, randomized, multicentric, double-blind study. *The Journal of Pain*. 2011;12:546-553.
78. Bharathi A, Sriniva NK, Reddy GR, Veeranjanyulu M, Sirisha A, Kamala P. Formulation and in vitro evaluation of diclofenac sodium sustained release matrix tablets using melt granulation technique. *Int J pharma bio sci*. 2011; (2)2.
79. Maiti S, Ranjit S, Sa B. Polysaccharide-Based Graft Copolymers in Controlled Drug Delivery. *Int J PharmTech Res*. 2010; (2):2.
80. Singh V, Kumar P, Sanghi R. Use of Microwave Irradiation in the Grafting Modification of the polysaccharides. *Progress in Polymer Science*. 2012; 37(2):340-364.
81. Narkar M, Sher P, Pawar A. Stomach specific controlled release gellan beads of acid-soluble drug prepared by ionotropic gelation method. *AAPS Pharma Sci Tech*. 2010;11: 267-277.
82. Hosseinzadeh H. Controlled release of diclofenac sodium from ph-responsive carrageenan-g-poly(acrylic acid) superabsorbent hydrogel. *J chem sci*. 2010; 122(4):651–659.
83. Shah DP, Jani GK. A newer application of physically modified gellan gum in tablet formulation using factorial design. *Ars Pharm*. 2010;51: 28-40.
84. Kumar A, Singh K, Ahuja M. Xanthan-g-poly(acrylamide): Microwave-assisted synthesis, characterization and in vitro release behaviour. *Carbo Polym*. 2009; 76: 261–267.
85. Sen G, Pal S. Microwave initiated synthesis of polyacrylamide grafted carboxy-methylstarch (CMS-g-PAM): Application as a novel matrix for sustained drug release. *Intern. J. Bio Macr*. 2009; 45:48–55.
86. Mishra A, James H, Pal S. Modified Okra mucilage using acrylamide & studied the effect of conc., reaction time and temperature. *Carbo Poly*. 2008;72: 608–615.
87. Hamcerencu M, Desbrieres J, Khoukh A, Popa M, Riess G. Synthesis and characterization of new unsaturated esters of gellan gum. *Carbohydrate Polymers*. 2007;71: 92–100.
88. Mishra A, Pal S. Polyacrylonitrile-grafted Okra mucilage: A renewable reservoir to polymeric materials. *Carbohy Poly*. 2007;68: 95–100.
89. Ali J, Khar R, Ahuja A. A textbook of dosage form design. Birla publications Pvt Ltd. Delhi. 2008; 3:100-107.
90. Pandey A, Rath B, AKD. Pharmaceutical Preformulation Studies with Special Emphasis on Excipients Compatibility. *Chem Inform*. 2012; 43(23): 20-5.
91. Casay G, Quattrocchi O, Hauck W, Cardoso AH, Belsky J. USP melting point reference standards: Evaluation of parameters that affect the melting point, USP Pharmacopeial Forum, PF39(4).
92. Nyola N, Jeyabalan GS. Simultaneous estimation of Azithromycin and Cefixime in Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients and Pharmaceutical dosage forms by Spectrophotometry. *Hygeia.J.D.Med*. 2012;4 (2):27-32.
93. Baka E, Comer JE, Takacs-Novak K. Study of equilibrium solubility measurement by saturation shake-flask method using hydrochlorothiazide as model compound. *J Pharm Biomed Anal*. 2008; 46(2): 335-41.
94. Xia XR, Baynes RE, Monteiro-Riviere NA, Riviere JE. Determination of the partition coefficients and

- absorption kinetic parameters of chemicals in a lipophilic membrane/water system by using a membrane-coated fiber technique. *Eur J Pharm Sci.* 2005; 24(1): 15-23.
95. Chatwal GR, Anand SK. Instrumental methods of chemical analysis. Himalaya publishing house, Delhi. 5th edition; 2002:2.149-2.159.
96. Mandal S, Ray R, Basu SK, Biswanath Sa. Evaluation of a Matrix Tablet Prepared with Polyacrylamide-g-Sodium Alginate Co-polymers and Their Partially Hydrolyzed Co-polymers for Sustained Release of Diltiazem Hydrochloride. *Journal of Biomaterials Science* 21 (2010) 1799–1814.
97. Sirisolla J, Ramanamurthy KV. Formulation and evaluation of cefixime trihydrate matrix tablets using HPMC, sodium CMC, ethyl cellulose. *Indian J Pharm Sci* 2015; 77(3):321-327.
98. Lobo MS, P. Costa. Modeling and comparison of dissolution profiles. *Eur. J. Pharm. Sci.* 2001; 13:123–133.
99. Indian Pharmacopoeia 2010 Volume II. Published by Indian Pharmacopoeia Commission, Ghaziabad. 1012-1014.
100. Nair AS, Vidhya KM, Saranya TR, Sreelakshmy KR, Nair SC. Mucoadhesive buccal patch of cefixime trihydrate using biodegradable natural polymer. *Int J Pharm Pharm Sci.* 2014; 6 (6): 366-371.
101. <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/cefixime#section=Computed Properties>
102. Jadhav P, Bhushan P, Pore Y, Kulkarni Anita, Kumar BK. Physicochemical and molecular modeling studies of cefixime–l-arginine–cyclodextrin ternary inclusion compounds. *Carbohydrate Polymers.* 2013; 98: 1317–1325.